

Inside computer music: analyzing the interaction of technology and musical creativity

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Abstract

This paper presents the final outcomes of the Arts and Humanities Research Council-funded project TaCEM (Technology and Creativity in Electroacoustic Music). It discusses how these outcomes combine very substantial text with extensive software and demonstration videos, and integrate historical and technical material with music analysis, using software to deliver an experience that is interactive, aural and playful. We discuss how further such analyses might be produced and outline tools being developed to facilitate this. We believe interactive aural analysis has a significant role to play as part of the future directions of electroacoustic music studies.

Central to our argument is the belief that electroacoustic music, or indeed any music, is best studied not in the abstract but in a way that directly links analytical ideas to aural experience, and one that incorporates playful interactive engagement with the music. In this spirit our paper is illustrated by a number of short video examples of interactive aural software in use. Links to these videos are provided at various places in this text. Alternatively, you can watch a video recording of the whole paper, with the video examples embedded. This can be found at: <https://youtu.be/47fuhdnX-NE>

1. Introduction

At a number of previous EMS conferences, starting with the 2013 EMS in Lisbon, we have presented analyses of specific works that form part of our Arts and Humanities Research Council-funded project TaCEM ('Technology and Creativity in Electroacoustic Music' -

<https://research.hud.ac.uk/institutes-centres/tacem/>). The project is now complete and its main output, the book *Inside Computer Music* (Clarke, Dufeu, Manning 2020), is published, comprising the final versions of these and other analyses. There are nine case-studies in total, focusing on works by John Chowning, Barry Truax, Philippe Manoury, Hildegard Westerkamp, Francis Dhomont, Trevor Wishart, Jonathan Harvey, Cort Lippe and Natasha Barrett. In this presentation we take the opportunity to look across all nine case-studies examining the analytical approaches taken and the problems and opportunities we encountered across the different works. We consider if more general lessons might be learnt about how such technical and musical issues can best be researched and presented and what would be involved in constructing further similar studies in the future. In TaCEM we set out with specific plans for using software alongside text in the production and dissemination of our research. These plans remained but evolved in significant new ways as the project developed. TaCEM also builds on the *Interactive Aural* approach to music analysis (Clarke 2012), again something discussed at earlier EMS conferences.

2. Technical Investigations

For each work, we investigated in depth the technical context, including the roles played by academic and commercial institutions and the composer's own background. We also studied in great detail the technical means required to produce the music. Indeed, we emulated many of the techniques employed in the works, some now obsolete or on the verge of obsolescence (for example, Barry Truax's GSX system, or GRM's SYTER used by Francis Dhomont). In some cases our emulations permit the recreation of the complete work and allow 'readers' to experiment with alternative options. Emulating the means used to produce the works involved a variety of tasks. Sometimes it meant researching documentary evidence when the technology itself was no longer extant. In other cases, the composers or others involved with the technology, were able to provide important information. With more recent examples, for example works programmed in Max, we often had access to the original code in a form that could be operated. In all cases we benefitted greatly from the goodwill and generosity of all those involved.

Not all analyses of electroacoustic works need to investigate the technical aspects in such detail. In our case the overarching topic of our project concerned the inter-relation of technological invention and musical creativity so it was essential. More generally it can be important when studying a work to have a good understanding of what Kofi Agawu has called 'the conditions of possibility' within which the music is created. In his book *Music as Discourse* he writes of generative analysis that: "The purpose of an analysis is to establish the conditions of possibility for a given composition" (Agawu 2009: 131). In the context in which Agawu was writing this meant primarily the possibilities afforded by the tonal system and accepted contrapuntal practice of a particular style, but in the context of computer music clearly the compositional possibilities afforded by the technologies employed are significant in understanding a work's 'conditions of possibility'. In other words, knowing what a composer could or could not do using their chosen technical setup is vital in informing our understanding of their ensuing musical choices.

Central to our interactive aural approach is that such technical information should not be presented simply using abstract verbal description or mathematical formulae. Interactive aural analysis is about experiencing ideas about the music and its technology through interactive

engagement. Readers can learn about these ‘conditions of possibility’ by playing with our emulations of the technology.

For example, in discussing the earliest piece in our collection, John Chowning’s *Stria* (1977), we present the FM synthesis technique (devised by the composer himself) used in this work both in general and in the specific configuration deployed in *Stria*. Alongside textual explanation we provide software models that allow readers to experiment with all the relevant parameters, hearing the musical implications of changing the settings for themselves. Live graphical displays also enrich the learning experience. You can find a short video demonstrating this software in action at: <https://youtu.be/dzQPQ00HBt4>

To take another contrasting example, this time from the most recent work in our collection *The Lock* by Natasha Barrett (2012): here sophisticated 3D spatialisation plays a vital role in shaping the music. Again, detailed textual discussion of these techniques in the book is accompanied in the software by our emulation of the spatial processes used by Barrett and readers can try moving sounds in space using an interactive graphic display and hear the results in real-time (our software provides for a variety of listening environments, from a multi-channel 3D setup to binaural playback through headphones). A short video demonstration can be found at: https://youtu.be/FML-KnUY_Cc

It is important to note that although the video demonstrations of the software are fixed, in practice readers using the software can manipulate all this for themselves, trying out alternatives interactively and hearing the results, perhaps rather as the composers themselves might have done.

3. Music Analysis

In tandem with such technical investigations, we undertook detailed musical analyses of each piece, again employing software to facilitate an interactive aural approach in which readers learn not just by encountering abstract analytical theories written in words, but primarily through playing with the musical materials for themselves. ‘Play’ is also an important part of music analysis for Kofi Agawu. In his seminal 2004 article “How we got out of analysis, and how to get back in again” he argues that we need to: “restore to [analysis] a measure of improvisation, liberate it from the requirement of making propositional statements, and reconfigure its epistemological requirements to privilege play” (Agawu 2004: 279). This is very much our intention in integrating interactive software into our case studies. Learning about this repertoire and developing knowledge about the relationship between technology and music is, we believe, best undertaken in a context that fully incorporates active, playful involvement. This is also highly relevant for current analytical concerns about making analysis more accessible, less elitist, and more democratic.

Our original expectation was that we would need to analyse the completed compositions by working largely with their final mixed versions and at the 2013 EMS in Lisbon we presented an interactive sonogram we were developing to assist us in doing this. In the event, for the works chosen for the TaCEM project, we were able, in different ways, to access the component parts of the works unmixed and use these in our analyses. In some cases this was achieved by re-synthesising the music using our emulations of the technology (e.g. Chowning, Truax). Other composers had extensive libraries of their source materials which they kindly made available to us (e.g. Dhomont, Westerkamp, Wishart). In further cases we

were able to adapt the original Max patches to recreate different components of a work (e.g. Barrett, Harvey, Lippe, Manoury). In all cases our musical analyses benefitted from the capability of using the individual components and processes that went to make up the work. Our software therefore allows users to manipulate these materials interactively as part of the analysis. Users can therefore, in a sense, follow in the footsteps of the composers.

We illustrate this with some brief examples of the analytical software in practice. To begin with, two examples illustrating the link between technical processes and musical structure.

Firstly, returning to *Stria*, our software enables readers to explore how Chowning shaped the large-scale musical structure by changing the parameters of the FM synthesis across the work. Readers can select specific parameters and track their evolution through the work, both aurally and visually. Our graphic interface make it easier and more intuitive for readers to see these processes and they can manipulate the parameters for themselves to understand Chowning's choices in the larger context of possibilities: <https://youtu.be/dXZZY1e6yY>.

Secondly, an interactive aural genealogy of the recorded and derived sounds that form the materials for Hildegard Westerkamp's *Beneath the Forest Floor*. It shows how the various sounds are derived and inter-related, and how they are built into the final structure of the work: <https://youtu.be/WCAAn47cpWSU>.

The next two examples show how complex textures can be analysed aurally and interactively using the software. The 'gamelan' section of Trevor Wishart's *Imago* is made up of many nested layers. The reader can explore these layers aurally, muting or soloing different components. A visual 'map' is provided but it is not simply abstract, it is one that can be heard and manipulated: <https://youtu.be/BAcktvEHpzc>.

Looking again at Natasha Barrett's *The Lock* on the large scale, our software facilitates an interactive exploration of the complex 3D spatialisation of multiple layers of sounds in this music. As in the previous Wishart example, layers can be soloed or muted and the sophisticated spatial processes can be followed both aurally and visually: <https://youtu.be/pwYxGE76rI4>.

Our investigations also included interviewing the composers and/or, where appropriate, those who had worked with them in the technical and musical realisation of each work. These interviews were recorded on video (which is significantly different from simply reading a transcript – though we do include some transcripts in the book) and are incorporated into the software for each case study. In this way, the opportunities for readers to work with the technical and musical materials for themselves are complemented by poetic information. Since a major concern of our project was the interaction of technological innovation and musical creativity, the fact that our interviews include not only the composers but also those who worked with them, including people researching and developing new technological resources (for example, Miller Puckette), facilitates discussion of this interaction. In some cases the technical innovation and its creative application were embodied in the same individual (e.g. Chowning, Truax, Wishart), but even where different people were involved in many cases there was significant overlap.

The following video is a collage of very brief extracts from some of our interviews: with the composers, Hildegard Westerkamp and John Chowning discussing their compositional decision making, and part of a demo of live processing in Jonathan Harvey's 4th *String Quartet* by his assistant for the work, Gilbert Nouno: https://youtu.be/GYt_ILq1m0.

4. Combining Text and Software

A central aspect of our project was investigating how best to communicate such findings, involving not only text, but also software, and video and audio recordings. We saw it as vital that these different media, and the various forms of knowledge they represent, should be integrated as fully as possible. In particular, it was important that the software should not be seen as an optional extra to the text: Equally important knowledge is conveyed both by the written word and by the interactive software which enables users to learn by playing with the technical and musical resources provided. One option might have been to include the text within the software. However, with such a substantial and detailed text (415 pages) this did not seem the optimum solution. Instead we used a number of means to integrate the text, published in the book, with the software. As technical and musical issues are discussed in the text frequent references are made to specific illustrations in the software. These are introduced and described in highlighted boxed areas within the text. The complexity of the software, and the computing power required, means that the software cannot simply be run online, it needs to be downloaded. This is a potential barrier for some readers who may not be inclined to go through this process unless they are convinced it is worthwhile. During the course of the project we therefore developed the idea of demonstration videos as an intermediary step, showing the value of the software. These can be played instantly from the OUP Companion Website. This idea grew in importance through the project resulting in the creation of, in total, 104 demonstration videos. They play a vital role in establishing the coherence of the whole package, linking discussions in the text to playful learning in the software. The videos take on a number of different roles: they provide short tutorials on how to operate the software; they give immediate illustrations of specific technical and/or musical features described in the text; and they offer a taste of what is to be found in more detail in the software, hopefully encouraging those who might otherwise be hesitant to venture further. The examples accompanying this paper come from some of these demo videos.

5. Future Directions of Interactive Aural Analysis

We very much hope that further such interactive aural studies will be produced, whether by ourselves or by other researchers, extending the repertoire of music covered and developing this approach further. The title of this conference is ‘Future Directions of Electroacoustic Music Studies’ and we believe that this type of analysis, integrating the listening experience and playful interactivity into analysis, has a vital role to play in the future of our field. This seems to fit well with what Simon Emmerson calls for in his keynote at this conference when he states that: “The abstraction of our music has focused on mapping – I mean that in the broadest literal sense – the making of a cartographic map, scaled into orthogonal Newtonian units of frequency and time – and if we are lucky, space. While useful for some specific tasks these are removed from perception, experience and *felt* time and space – or should that be place.” Emmerson therefore suggests “a shift from ‘mapping’ to ‘wayfinding’ (after Ingold), from hovering above an abstraction to experiencing the flux from within. In our subject field it makes more sense to ‘study the music’ through experiencing it” (Emmerson 2021).

What is involved in developing such studies? Clearly it is time-consuming, but so is music analysis more generally: it requires very detailed attention to the music. Part of our current project, IRiMaS (Interactive Research in Music as Sound -

<https://research.hud.ac.uk/institutes-centres/irimas/>)¹, involves creating a Toolbox for Interactive Aural Analysis (TIAALS), software designed to enable musicologists to put together their own analyses, incorporating audio, video, interactive sonograms, audio descriptor maps, interactive analytical charts of all kinds, into an integrated analytical document (Dufeu, Takahashi, Roebel and Clarke 2019). Our aim is to make this as straightforward as using Word or PowerPoint. We hope to present more on this at a future conference, once it is completed. This video presents a short introduction to just a few of the possibilities afforded by the TIAALS software: <https://youtu.be/180wwT-JxwQ>.

Of course, if an analysis involves creating the type of emulations of technology we have used in TaCEM, this does need good technical knowledge and programming skills. (In TaCEM everything was coded in Max with the addition of some additional specially written externals.) And this task is different for each work and needs researching individually. On the music analysis side, having the collaboration of the composers and assistants is a great benefit and things would need to be approached somewhat differently otherwise. It may not be easy, but it is possible, and we believe the benefits far outweigh the challenges. It results in analyses that take into account the process of composition followed by the composer as part of the creative process.

The interactive aural approach makes both the technology and the musical analysis more accessible and more meaningful. In terms of teaching and learning, as we said in our paper at the EMS conference in Florence, it offers the potential to bring together historical, technical, analytical and compositional study into an integrated whole, with resources that are engaging and relevant. We very much hope others will engage in similar projects and we are happy to discuss our experience and advise if needed.

6. References

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